

PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT AND THE CHALLENGES OF LOCAL GOVERNMENT IN NIGERIA: ISSUES AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract

The gains and losses of any organization is a function of the human resources that pilot the affairs of such organization. The onuses as to how an organization thrives are at their whims and caprices; they constitute the greatest assets of any organization. The supply of labour, technical and professional skills, which are germane for effective and efficient planning and implementation of development policies, programmes, projects and daily activities are their sole responsibility. Very instructively, personnel administration relates to the overall organizations planning process by which the organization tries to ensure that it has the right number of persons and the right kind of people, at the right time and at the right place performing functions, which are economically useful and which satisfy the needs of the organization and provide satisfaction to the individual involved. This study interrogates the challenges of development of local government in Nigeria from the purview of personnel management. The work examines recruitment process into local authority, statutory provisions for training and retraining, staffing, amongst others, as it based its theory on decentralized development as framework of analysis. It concludes that local government personnel management is frost with nonchalance, poor staffing and challenges of re-entrants of trainees.

Key Words: Personnel, Management, Local Government, Development, Recruitment.

Background to the study

Agba *et al* (2014), reference Malami (2008), as they maintained that, Government is a great responsibility and only persons who have carefully prepared themselves and have a high sense of self-discipline and responsibility should aspire to lead. For indeed, government is an awesome responsibility and trust which if abused or betrayed, holds untold political, economic and social consequences, loss of lives and sufferings for the people of the country as a whole.

Thus, local Government is recognized as the third tier of government in Nigeria and it is the closest government to the people at the grassroots providing essential services to the people. It is the most accessible to the people out of all the other tiers of government (Aibieyi, 2011). Local government as a third tier system of government in Nigeria was established to bring government closer to the people at the grass-root level. It is a way of coordinating and managing the affairs of government at the local level (Ola and Tonwe, 2005). Mawhood (1993) defined local government as bodies separated by law (and have) local representatives (and) formal power to decide on a range of public matters. Their right to make decisions is entrenched by the law and can only be altered by a new legislation. They have resources, which is said to be subject to the stated limits, and are spent and invested at their discretion. As noted by Ajayi (2013) he posits that this class of people cut across ethnic, religious and regional divides.

Local government can be defined as a political sub-division of a nation or state which is constituted by law and has substantial control of local affairs, including the powers to improve taxes or to exact labour for prescribed purpose. To this extent it is also interesting to know that local government is a legal entity which could sue and be sued. Decisions taken and their enforcement are done in a manner that follows rules and regulations

It has often been argued and questioned by many political scientists regarding the reason why we need a local administration in the midst of central and state governments. The question is, why the need for local government administration at all? As this question puzzle many renowned scholars, some has relentlessly tried some justifications by affirming that local administration involves the training of local people for high political responsibilities and the provision of social services. However, the objectives of local government are far from being realized for several reasons. Thus, the study intends to look at personnel management in relations to local government

performances in Nigeria.

There is a classical relationship between the capacity of local government and their statutory roles of developments in their locality. The quality of personnel equipped for the local government will determine the extent to which the arm of government will be able to respond to its statutory responsibility. A local authority that is frost with unqualified and unethical personnel will frustrate the expectations of the government in the pursuit of grass root development.

One of the cardinal limitations of local authority is the pursuit of local developments in contemporary time is lack of well equipped, sound and ethically driven personnel in the management of local authority. This is evident in the prevalence of lackadaisical attitude to local policy of developments, indiscipline and unethical practices such as gross mismanagements of local fund, corruption in its entirety, absenteeism, poor attitude to work, etc.

Thus to effectively deal with personnel management and the challenges of local developments it is pertinent to begin with the recruitment process, training and retraining of staff for capacity building, and the ethical discipline required to function in the capacity so required to drive home the goal of local developments.

Theoretical Discourse

Theory of Decentralized Development

This study relies on the theory of decentralized development as a framework of analysis. Resler (1968) defines decentralization as the ideological dimension of state apparatus. This means that as a state apparatus, decision making system is designed to have a parameter to reflect and influence the structure; it depicts how resources, authority, information and decision process flow. Decentralization simply means, in this perspective the concentration of decision making in a supreme authority in any polity.

Development is all pervading. In other words, it is the ultimate goal of any society or humanity. It is the ability of government to meet or rather satisfies the basic human needs like food, shelter, education and health as well as the psychological need of man. The provision of roads, transportation, communication etc, is all part of development which government must meet. The major instrument for achieving development in any given society is local government. To do this end, the central government creates room for accelerated development.

Therefore, there is need for aerial distribution of power amongst the three levels of

government (federal, state and local). The aerial distribution of powers should be all embracing, that is, vertical or horizontal. The participation of local administration in the development process in any country on the nature of the polity in such country under democratic governance, participation of local administration is more attained as democratic values are promoted.

Egonmwan (1984) states that "the 1976 Local Government Reforms" was rooted on the ideology of grassroot democracy which the political leaders saw as not only important and desirable in itself, but as crucial element in the political programme of the Federal Military Government to return to the democratic rules. This tendency is to ensure the participation of the people in the democratic process which surpasses the democratic process representation.

Community - Politics Approach

This approach of decentralization sees equality of citizens on group participation in politics, in which participants are subject to the rule of the game. In effect, participants must abide by all the conditions of the system. There are bound to be demands from different groups on the micro-political system (local administration) and this may result to conflict on how to perform the function of an impartial adjudication. In the course of performing this function, the local government council has to regulate access to it according to the disparities in the political, capital resources, power, status and strategies of these competing groups. The council must possess the capacity to regulate the demands on it by these competing groups so as to avoid conflict in the area. This is what Egonmwan (1984) referred to as "assumed shifting equilibrium of power."

Community politics approach is centered on the location of community power. Although there is confusion about decentralization, but it is equal to community autonomy or democracy in a nation. The critics of the community politics approach to decentralization have warned that decentralization should be seen as participation in terms of intensity and scope in modern system rather than democratic characteristics.

Administrative Structure of Local Government

For the purposes of effectiveness and efficiency in service deliver, local Government councils are expected to have six mandatory departments. These are; i. The Department of Personnel Management; ii. The Department of Finance, supply, planning, Research and statistics; and iii. Not more than four "Operations" department reflecting the basic functions and area of concern to Local Government, namely:- Education; Agriculture and Natural Resources; Works, Housing, Land and Survey; and Medical and Health. Any other expansion of departments can be accommodated

under divisions and branches which can further be separated into sections to reflect specialized activities within a sub-professional/professional/ divisions/ branches/sections of department. Local Governments have their heads, each bearing a functional title reflecting his/her profession in the area of specialization.

The Recruitment System of Local Government

The rules and regulations guiding the personnel Management system in the Local government service are embodied in a document, referred to as unified Local Government Staff Regulations. The statutory body charged with the onus of the recruitment promotion, transfer, discipline, welfare and training of personnel in the local Government system is known as the Local Government Service Commission.

There are two categories of staff in the Local Government service. The first category of staff ranging from Grade Levels 07 and above are recruited by the Local Government service commission and posted to Local Government Councils. These categories of staff are referred to as the unified staff. The lower level of staff from grade levels 01-06 are to be recruited by the Local government councils. The onus of recruitment, discipline and promotion of these categories of staff is incumbent upon the Junior Staff Management Committee (JSMC). This committee is a mandatory requirement for all local government councils to establish. Matters of promotion considered by the Junior Staff Management Committee are expected to be conveyed to the Local Government service commission not later than the 30th of the subsequent month with the minutes of the relevant meeting of the committee.

The point has to be stressed since majority of the country's local governments are rural local governments and so are bereft of the basic life-sustaining infrastructure which would attract well- trained professionals.

Apart from the financial problem of Local Governments, there is lack of executive capacity, particularly in the technical fields, like agriculture and estate evaluation. Egonmwan (1984) stressed the point that the dearth of skilled manpower to execute major programmes in these fields is a major problem militating against the efficiency and effectiveness of local government. This position is reinforced by the notion held by most professionals, including seasoned administrators that the unified Local Government service is not an ideal place to work in because of its rural nature and more importantly, the level of notoriety associated with the local Government system in Nigeria. There is the fervent desire of people, especially professionals to

choose to work in cities festooned with all the paraphernalia of modernity. This local brain-drain has brought about the lack of well-trained professionals in most rural local government areas in Nigeria. According to Ayuba (2012), he asserted the disparity in the rural and urban development in Nigeria can be said to be attributable to the apparent neglect by government for not discouraging the rural-urban drift. Ayuba referenced Ballara (1981) and Oyaide (1989) as he agreed that one of the factors responsible for the rural-urban migration is the absence of basic social facilities in the rural areas. Ani (1999) added that it has also been equally argued that most problems of large cities are caused by rural-urban migration.

Ola & Tonwe (2006), expressed the opinion that the poverty of personnel was worsened by the poor planning for educational development. Poverty was not restricted to the personnel alone, but was reflected in the availability of funds for implementing the planning of educational programmes. The problem is more acute in the areas that are very critical for effective service delivery such as engineers, doctors, accountants, auditors, estate surveyors, architects, town planners and pharmacists etc. This could be the reason why Oaikhena *et. al.* (2013), posits that, the effective development of the human resources of an enterprise is one of the most vital contributions to the future and long-term growth of development and survival of any establishment.

There is no gainsaying the fact that manpower is the most essential of all the resources required for the translation of the lofty objectives of rural transformation into reality. Man is the engine room of development. It is an established fact that the value of any organization would improve as qualified employees are attracted, trained and developed in the organization. The asset value of the organization would decrease as skilled staff leaves the organization. This could be the reason why Agbato (2010) assert that, the best or ideal organization is achieved when the individuals see how their activities contribute to the dominant objectives of the organization. Organizations, whether public or private, are prone to jeopardy when there is no adequate human resource and manpower administration. Consequent upon the available premise, the disturbing need arises for manpower management and development as a sine-qua-non for improved performance which ensures optimum productivity and reproduction of a near perfect society. A sustainable use of our natural resources largely depends on the societal capacities of citizens and communities for inter-sectorial and long-term intergenerational responsibility (PDHRE, 2006)

Despite the available human capital, civil service in Nigeria has neither been properly

managed nor the available human resources administered effectively and efficiently. Nwanolue (2012) opined that, this ugly trend has fetched the service a bad name over the years. In most cases, staff development is neglected or overlooked entirely. This is usually due to the corruption in the service. Cases abound where funds ranging into millions and billions of naira, meant for staff development have been embezzled by individuals and groups in charge, without any serious actions taken to that effect. This could be the reason why Agbato (2010) posits that, there should be a complete change in value and attitude of upper and middle level management. This he said, are likely to lead to poor and ineffective communication since, more often, there is a deliberate filtering of information passed by the “powers that be.

On the other hand, there have been situations where some staff are never given the opportunity for years to undergo training at all. It is now a simple understanding that staff training in the public domain has become a matter of “face-looking” (Nwanolue, 2012). Alluding to this fact was, Oaikhena (2011) when he referenced Tonwe (2004), that systematic training in habits of industry is an effective system of cooperation between workmen and foremen, as it is a faster method to produce not only the work but, better quality work, with fewer mistakes and less scrap, this method he said, increases attention and concentration in the work place.

The local government system in Nigeria has been widely acknowledged as one tier of government that has been grossly marred by ineptitude. While some see it as a result of political interference, leadership style, corruption etc, others see it as a result of weakness, un-readiness and unwillingness of the staffers of the institution to do their job. However, in either ways these opinions are expressed, the underlying and undeniable facts are that something is fundamentally wrong with the system that has left us where we are today. Ekpo (1989) stated that the lack of adequate emphasis on manpower development as a tool for development in Nigeria on the part of government as well as the organized private sector could not be farfetched from the lack of understanding of both the concept and methods application of manpower development in a post-colonial Nigerian State, in which the process of human resources development for national growth was distorted by colonialism with the attendant negative orientation that was injected into political leadership. Nwanolue & Iwuoha (2012) emphasized that the challenges of manpower development in Nigeria’s Local Government System are myriads. These challenges according to them include; Colonial experience, Leadership style, Poor human capital planning, Corruption.

In the local authority, there are too many square pegs in round holes. The helpless and confused structural contradictions and general malfunctioning of public businesses and institutions are mainly the reason why things are not moving smoothly in the public circle. Meritocracy has been thrown overboard in the nation's public institutions. Those issues such as promotion and even recruitment and staff welfare are now done on preferential basis. Anazodo (2008) stated that there has continued to be the unlikelihood of the attainment of the purposes for which the public sectors in Nigeria were established, reasons being that some senior public servants lack professional depth and often fail to provide any chain of continuity in government over the longer term. From the above, it could therefore be argued that there were distortions in both the concept and methods of application (i.e. utilization) of manpower development in the Nigerian Local Government System as it was oriented towards serving capitalist interest which was consequently left in the hands of self-serving political leaders. In view of the numerous weaknesses associated with the local government system, successive governments had embarked on a number of manpower development reforms to address these problems. The various reform efforts have focused on the search for a more responsive, reoriented, restructured and effective manpower development and its attendant utilization. In spite of these numerous reforms, it is sad to note that in reality the efforts have not yielded the desired result. For instance, the Nigerian local government system has often been accused of being short sighted, inefficient, incompetent, insensitive and conservative; and lack of imagination.

A comparative institutional reforms analysis conducted by Nwanolue & Iwuoha (2012) showed that the Nigeria's Local Government System has enjoyed more reforms than any other tiers of government in the history of Nigeria, yet the system is still marred by ineptitude. For instance, in the ministries, the permanent secretary who is a career professional is supposed to be the back bone of the politically appointed minister and this continued even to the local government system where we have the head of service. But in return what happens is that at the local government level most of these civil servants are illiterates whom either by any means found themselves in the system without the requisite qualifications. The pertinent question therefore becomes how well we can in the midst of these problems, better enhance and strengthen our local government system through adequate manpower utilization.

Manpower Development And Manpower Utilization

Indeed the importance of manpower development and its corresponding utilization especially at the local governments has become more obvious given the growing complexity of the work environment, the rapid change in organizations and technological advancement which further necessitates the need for training and development of personnel to meet the trend challenges. Manpower development helps to ensure that organizational members possess the knowledge and skills they need to perform their jobs effectively, take on new responsibilities, and adapt to changing conditions. It is important to note that, when properly utilized; i.e. ensuring that skills developed are placed in the exact areas of specialty, will consequently help in improving quality of work performance, customer satisfaction, productivity, morale, management succession, business development and profitability.

Manpower/human resource training however, can be defined as training of people in developing their capability on their jobs. Beach (1980) defined training as the organized procedure by which people learn from a definite purpose. The purpose of training according to Beach is to achieve a change in behavior of those trained. Training is a vital aspect of organizational needs. Appropriate and regular training equips the staff with organizational values, goals and norms, impart new skills, techniques and knowledge of one's jobs, increases problem-solving capabilities, and hence raises the level of workers performance. Above all, training keeps the staff abreast with the demands of a fast changing society.

The issue of utilization of developed manpower is aptly and unavoidably important if the sole objective of manpower development is to be achieved (Ozigbo, 2010). There is need for an optimum utilization of developed manpower in organizations (private or public) for the benefit of the stakeholders – the organization, the staff and the economy at large. Ubeku (1985) pointed out that training is a continuous process in any organization. He wrote that investment on training and development are wise investments. Osiyi (1985) made it clear that no organization rises, above the technical competence of its personnel, therefore any organization or Local Government that does not take the development of her staff through training seriously must be heading for some problems. The concept of Manpower embraces the totality of human resources within an organization and it determines the level and extent of development of such organization. It is important to note that all the activities of any organization are initiated and determined by the persons that make up the organization. In other words, offices, computer equipment and all that the organization uses are unproductive and useless except they are put by human effort and

direction. Human resource development and utilization in both public and private organization has become extra ordinarily important, especially in the changing world, that one (an employee) who was productive sometime in the past may loose meaning (become unproductive) sometime in the future due to the changing time and/or environment. Sometimes, it happens that the changes that occur in an organization or the job, which an employee may be required to carry, demands a kind of knowledge so strange that the employee could not produce. In other to change, with the changing environment and work requirements, organizations must develop their manpower very well so that right the person is at the right place at the right time in order to meet organizational goals and changes.

One serious problem according to Chukwuemeka (2003) confronting public personnel managers is the most effective method of matching people with job. Experts, over the period have grappled with the problem of whether job should be designed to suit the individual or get the individual to fit into a job position. This calls for taking strategic steps or actions and this action is manpower training for development. An effective, human resources according to Ojo (1997) is central and vital to organization effectiveness. It requires an understanding of a range of factors involved in the manpower planning processes and specific roles of the various factors involved in the planning in line with the organizational, goals and objectives. More so, human resource development and utilization should be a critical concern of organizations particularly, the personnel officers, who should bear in mind while planning for human resource, that only intelligent, capable hands could successfully achieve the organizational goals.

Furthermore, Chukwuemeka added that, the onus is for them to ensure that at each point in time, their organization must have the right caliber of employee, in the right number and quality to perform the appropriate tasks for the purpose of achieving the overall organizational goals. The important roles of manpower come into focus both in peacetime and when the nation is at war (Oguniyi 1992). Adequate and qualified manpower is the measure of an organization's strength, security and wellbeing. The human resource of any organization holds the key to its survival, advancement and future development. This is why Renesis (1967) pointed out the importance of manpower and the need for its planning in an organization cannot be over emphasised. Accordingly, the development of a concept of executive action embodies the skills, of influencing and controlling the nature and direction of change. It also involves persuasive and continuous executive function of complex process of perceptions, analysis, conceptual thought,

communication, decision and action. Nwachukwu (1988), notwithstanding viewed manpower development and utilization, as referring to the projection of future requirements for a given number of people, that is, people with specific skills to meet the demand of various sections of the economy.

In other words, the authors tried to emphasize that in an organization manpower development programmes must be in accordance with the organization's broad objectives. In most organization, developing human resources strategy becomes a search for those candidates, who can contribute to the realization of the organizational objectives.

Organizations are becoming more independent upon people because they are rapidly involved in more complex economic, political, and socio-cultural environment. The more organizations get involved in more complex and technical skills in the manufacturing, marketing and sales of products and services, the more vulnerable such organizations will be to critical shortages of the right human resources. This implies that the managers in future will increasingly have to be more skilled in how to select or train their subordinates. They will not necessarily employ people but rather, they will be engaged in employing high sophisticated, trained individuals. It then becomes a matter of economic objectives to improve human resource planning and development systems. The assumption underlying organizational growth is that the nature of jobs will change overtime; implying that such changes must be continuously monitored in order to ensure that the right kind of human resources can be recruited or developed to do these jobs. Following these development assumptions, manpower planning and development then, forms the component that facilitate the actual process of the growth and development of the people who are brought into the organization with the purpose of removing ineffectiveness in skills and other phenomena that neglect the need for a new growth direction.

The Issue of Merit as a Criterion for Manpower Development in The Local Government System

Various governments in Nigeria have facilitated the training of personnel for both the public and private sector. According to Onasanya (1999) the industrial fund act of 1971 was aimed at funding a training system that would create a pool of trained indigenous manpower for the economy, providing a sort of consultancy on training needs to the various employers and encouraging them to establish their own training centers. While, Agbator (2010) posits that knowledge can come to us through several avenues – personal experience, perception or even

through the experience of others. To achieve this thrust of the interrelatedness, the mechanism in which trainees are selected should be one devoid of corrupt tendencies. This is because if it is not justiceably made, it may amount to the popular saying "... as one bad apple in a basket...", that is to say that if any of the policy areas is devoid of merit in the selection for training, it would undoubtedly bring to futility each of the others. For example, the development of incentive or reward systems affects the ability of an organization to respond to rapid change.

Similarly, communication between administrators in local government ensures that all other policy areas are linked to one another through building and reinforcing the appropriate organizational culture around the organizational mission. Onasanya (1999) reiterated that, identifying and assessing training needs should depend upon the corporate plan of the organization. The functions of local government according to Nwata (1995), is classified as obligatory and discretionary, such functions include agricultural programme, animal husbandry building and communication, education administration, fishery, forestry, small scale industries, medical services, security disposal etc. As a result manpower development has become an important emphasis for all governments' components especially the local government in an age of global competition in which all large-scale organization must compete for resources whether they are in the private or public sector (Adamolekun, 2011).

Capacity Building of Personnel in Local Government

According to Beesley and Shebby (2010), capacity building can be defined straightforwardly as a process for strengthening the management and governance of an organization so that it can effectively achieve its objectives and fulfill its mission. From past experience, it is common knowledge that the local government has the weakest capacity to initiate and manage rural development programmes. This is due to the fact that the quality and quantity of human resources available at the local government level is seriously insufficient. Capacity building, becomes an intervention that strengthens an establishment's ability to fulfill its mission by promoting sound management, strong governance, and persistent rededication to achieving results. Most official who perform their functions without the relevant qualifications, perform poorly. As a result, available resources for accelerated and sustainable rural development are inefficiently utilized for the purposes intended, thus leaving the local governments today without a reasonable number of qualified Accountants, Engineers, Medical Doctors, Property Valuers or

even Economists. This could be the reason why Onasanya (1999) agreed that education is the systematic and continuous way of instructing a person with a view to imparting knowledge into such a person so as to develop him mentally, physically and spiritually.

Strategies for Capacity Building in Local Government

It has become imperative to adopt urgent measures aimed at raising the executive capacity profile of local governments if they are to fulfill the rural development role which has been assigned to this level of government. There have been annual staff development plan in line with the local government capacity development plan. This has become imperatives due to some urgent measures. These measures include:

- Staff development at local government and community level must be intensified.
- .Training in planning and management of rural development must be hastened as this will form the basis upon which the local government human capacity will be strengthened.
- Training to be undertaken through on-the-job, in-service and academic methods through joint collaboration between the federal, state and local governments, donor agencies, foundations, NGOs, CBOs, SMOs, etc.
- Conduct of a staff audit as a first step with a view to determining areas where there is excess capacity and shortfalls which are to be addressed.
- Utilize critical expertise that is available from the pool of retired state and federal officers in designated professional areas for specified periods on contract basis.
- Carry out recruitment of suitably qualified persons to improve the quality of staff available at the local government level.

Thus, capacity building is not limited to training personnel or the provision of technical assistant (TA), but may include overhauling systems, remodeling physical infrastructure, recruiting new personnel, and improving the efficiency of the use of existing resources (Wing 2004).

The experience in capacity building in relation to accelerated and sustainable rural development at the local government level in the past has shown the following characteristics:

- Failure to build capacity which can be sustained;
- Failure to address critical national/local objectives;
- Capacity building not treated as a priority, which must be a continuous process/efforts;

- Lack of formulation of coherent strategies with a realistic time frame.

Consequently, for capacity building to improve at the local government to ensure accelerated and sustainable development the following measures must be adopted as a way forward:

- Capacity assessment/profile;
- Analysis of the existing capacity problems;
- Assessment of past approaches to capacity building;
- Strengthening the existing system;
- Technology transfer.

Finally, there are two critical issues related to capacity building at the local government level for accelerated and sustainable rural development namely: capacity retention and capacity retrieval.

Capacity Retention involves keeping those trained in critical areas in the local government; curtailing loss through brain-drain; keeping them constantly exposed to new knowledge, tools and techniques in their various fields and providing, conducive work environment as well as the tools to work.

Capacity Retrieval entails making concerted efforts through policy measures to retrieve or bring back home those who have out migrated.

Perennial Problems of Local Government personnel management.

1. General Indiscipline

According to Okhakhu, (2012), indiscipline refers to the deliberate non-conformity with the rules, regulations and values of any given society. In Nigeria for instance, the problems of indiscipline continue to rise in geometrical proportion in spite of the many years of independence. Indiscipline is rampantly perceived and well pronounced among the workers in local government. The senior officers who travel to their families away from their offices on Friday, return very late the following Monday or may decide to stay back till Tuesday, and the junior members of staff who directly or indirectly observe this more often than not are in the habit of playing truant with the jobs. Little or no commitment to duty has become a rule rather than an exception. Offices have been turned to market places where officers hawk their goods freely. The rules that guide moral conduct and professional ethics seem to have, at worst, become cobweb that is too weak to tame the monstrous activities of the workers. Indiscriminate lustful desires are noticeable among the workers. The official relationship between super ordinates and subordinates has been stained.

Strict instructions handed down from top echelon to the bottom are either not followed or treated with levity, as a result of the immoral relationship between the boss and subordinates. Official duties are seen as an extension of private leisure. Laissezfaire attitude to work has arrested the efficiency of local government and has drastically affected its performance.

. Undue Interference

The degree of external influence and intrusion in the local government affairs by the higher levels of government is worrisome and needs re-evaluation. Situation where the state governor unconstitutionally dissolves the entire elected council's officers without proper investigations on spurious allegations is not good for the future of local government administration in the country. Such external interference indeed subverts democratic process and undermines constitutional authority at the grassroots level. The crux of the matter is the 'almighty' power and misuse of i.e. enjoyed by the state government over local governments. Practically, and in the true sense, local government in Nigeria lacks autonomous financial power. Local government is now considered an extension of state's ministry. The inherent nature of this problem has caused subservience, a situation where local government waits for the next directives from state government before the former could think of, let alone embarking on development projects.

Conclusion

Personnel is a critical factor in the attainment of the goals of an organization, hence good organizational structure does not by itself, guarantee good performance. Personnel is life to the existence, survival and development of an organization as food is to man; since all the activities of any organization are initiated and determined by the persons who make up that organization. Plant, offices, computers, automated equipment and all else that a modern firm uses are unproductive except for human efforts and direction. This is why personnel have been defined as persons employed in an organization to perform some kind of work or task including the management of them. However, the ability of personnel to contribute to the attainment of the goals of an organization such as the local government depends to a large extent on how well they are managed. This is because all the task of management managing the human component is central and most important task because all else depend on how well it is done. Simply put, the personnel of an organization have to be properly managed for them to be able to make maximum contribution to the organization. Such organization may be the local government council.

Local government is a unit of government below the central, regional and state government, established by law to exercise political authority through a representative council within a defined area. It is also a system of public administration at a local level, charged with the responsibility of bringing the people at the grassroots closer to the government. It involves a philosophical commitment to a democratic participation in the governing process at the local level. The expediency for the creation of local government stems from the need to facilitate development at the grassroots. Its importance, however, is a function of its ability to generate sense of belongingness, safety and satisfaction among its populace. To achieve these important changes, the seeming impediments, in the context of problems of personnel management, such that have infringed on its performance of functions, duties and responsibilities, should be dealt with.

Recommendation

- a. It is important to note however that while the government deals with the environmental problems confronting the people, the individual should make adequate efforts to imbibe a high spirit of discipline and patience which is the hallmark of civilization and this will make our local government fair better in areas of efficiency and effectiveness.
- b. The elite at the local government level should show sufficient commitment to making the local government system work in the interest of all in the society.
- c. Local government administration should place more emphasis on staff training, retraining and developments. This will enhance employee performance and productivity irrespective of their quality/qualification on entry point. In this era of globalization, competition is the order of the day and local governments cannot be left out.
- d. It is important to emphasize the role and support of top management personnel, which is also critical and important in ensuring a robust and good employee relation management system in the local government.
- e. Adequate funding should be made available for local government administration. As public accountability and transparency is encouraged amongst administrators.

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